

Teaching Physical Education to Hearing Impaired Students: The Case of Ambo Lazarist Catholic Deaf School, Western Ethiopia

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Abstract

The main objective of this research is to investigate the educational practice of Physical Education for Students with hearing impairments at Ambo Lazarist Catholic School. Researchers employed mixed methods, specifically embedded design. The populations of the study were 58 Students with hearing impairments, 1 physical education teacher, and 2 school principals. Comprehensive and purposive sampling were used. The findings of this study indicated that the level of identification, teaching strategies, and opportunities at Ambo Lazarist Catholic School for the Deaf for students with hearing impairments is low. No audiologist knew about identifying the magnitude of hearing impairment in Students with hearing impairment, and the teaching strategies of the school had some hindrances like rigidity in their teaching methods. Although there is a commitment to developing the educational practice of physical education for students with hearing impairment in this particular school, there is still work to be done in the future, like the school's practice of identifying students with hearing impairment, which needs further attention among all stakeholders, and awareness-creation strategies that should be designed for families and other stakeholders so that they can support and encourage the practice of physical education for Students with hearing impairment.

Keywords: physical education, practice, student with hearing impairment.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Study

Adapted Physical Education (APE) is an individualized program of developmental activities, exercises, games, and sports designed to meet the unique physical education needs of individuals (Luo, 2000). And also, as suggested by the school board of Brevard County (2006) the APE domain applies to all populations with special disabilities.

Luo (2000) notes that approximately 3000 years ago in China, significant events related to the development of APE were identified, emphasizing the therapeutic application of gymnastics for people with disabilities. Subsequently, in 1879, Harvard implemented corrective physical education aimed at addressing specific pathological issues. Between WWI and WWII, the growth of physical therapy and adaptive sports began to take shape. During the 1940s, major transformations were introduced in physical education at various universities, public schools, and specialized institutions. The course content replaces calisthenics, gymnastics, and corrective physical education with games, sports, and rhythmic activities tailored to the unique needs of the students.

In Africa, Onyewadume (2007) notes that there is a significant lack of information in international journals and on the World Wide Web regarding the status and practice of adapted physical activity across different African nations. Nevertheless, the integration of field-adapted physical activity into the physical education curriculum of certain higher institutions in Africa began in the early 1980s (Onyewadume, 2007). Prior to the 1980s, experts in physical education and recreation were prepared to instruct physical education and different sports skills solely to individuals without disabilities. The Ethiopian Constitution accepts international declarations and conventions, and states education as a human right. Also, as a country Ethiopia aims at an education system that is open to all learners, regardless of poverty, gender, ethnic background, language, learning difficulties, and impairments. The principle behind this policy is that all children and students are included. The Government wants to ensure that there is equity and fairness in the Ethiopian education system (MOE, 2016).

In Ethiopia, similar to other countries of the world physical education is given as one type of school subject like biology, chemistry, math, etc. The physical education curriculum in schools caters to students ranging from kindergarten to university level (Gizachew, 2012). Additionally, the Growth and Transformation Plan II 2015/16 - 2020/21 (GTP) focuses on providing special

attention and support to children with special needs to ensure they initiate and sustain their education. The notion that can be deduced from the preceding paragraphs concerning Ethiopia is that, while there is a robust dedication to embracing international policies, conventions, and declarations for students with disabilities, the actual execution of those policies, conventions, and declarations is notably lacking. Furthermore, this study sought to explore the educational methods of physical education for students with hearing loss in specialized schools. Additionally, the researcher examined aspects that can be regarded as the fundamental components of teaching physical education to students with Hearing Impairment. The Ambo Lazarist Catholic School for the Deaf was established in 2005 E.C. by a Catholic religious group called the Ethiopian Deaf Project. Initially, it was instructing students with hearing impairment in Grades 5-8 until it transitioned to teaching students with hearing impairment in Grades 1-4 in 2008.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

This research is focused on the educational practice of physical education for students with hearing impairment at Ambo Lazarist Catholic School for the Deaf.

The Maryland State's National Association of Sport and Physical Education (NASPE) states that physical education can act as a means to assist students in acquiring the knowledge, attitudes, motor skills, behavioral skills, and confidence required to engage in and sustain a physically active lifestyle (Mason, 2009). Thus, when an individual observes the advantages of physical education, he/she can understand that everyone in this world ought to enjoy these benefits fairly. The primary focus of the researchers in the paragraph above is that every individual, including those with disabilities, should have equal chances to engage in physical education activities. Additionally, in our society, individuals should no longer have to live in isolation because of insufficient physical and motor skills necessary for independent domestic and recreational activities (Fekede, 2012).

Moreover, students with Hearing Impairment require specific considerations in the design and execution of PE programs offered to them. However, if that is not the case, they won't be able to engage safely and effectively, thereby missing out on the physical, social, and psychological advantages that a quality PE program provides (Fekede, 2012). Furthermore, the researcher is interested in exploring the connections between the identification, teaching approaches, opportunities, and obstacles faced by Ambo Lazarist Catholic School for the Deaf in relation to

the physical education practices for students with hearing impairments. The following are leading questions that are guiding the research to know the educational practice of physical education to students with hearing impairment in Ambo Lazarist Catholic School for the Deaf.

- What identification method did the school utilize to recognize students with Hearing Impairment?
- What instructional methods did the school implement to teach Physical Education to students with Hearing Impairment?
- What types of opportunities did the school provide for students with Hearing Impairment in their Physical Education instruction?
- What types of difficulties did students with Hearing Impairment encounter in their Physical Education learning?

2. Review of Related Literature

This chapter basic concept of adapted physical education for students with disabilities (SWDs) and the educational practice of APE including identification, teaching strategies, opportunities, and challenges in teaching APE for Students with disabilities including those with a hearing impairment that are stated in many works of literature have been reviewed.

2.1. Adapted Physical Education

Adapted Physical Education is an individualized program of developmental activities, exercises, games, and sports designed to meet the unique physical education needs of individuals (Luo, 2000).

2.1.1. Goals of Adapted Physical Education

As per the Maryland State's National Association of Sport and Physical Education (NASPE), "physical education can function as a means for assisting students in acquiring the knowledge, attitudes, motor skills, behavioral skills, and confidence required to embrace and sustain a physically active lifestyle." The results of an effective physical education program encompass the enhancement of students' physical skills, fitness related to health, self-worth, and overall pleasure in engaging in physical activities (Mason, 2009). According to the Brevard County school board (2006), the adaptive physical education domain is relevant to all individuals with disabilities. The goals align with those of standard physical education and athletics. Movement,

skills, and sports ought to be taught, but the equipment, rules, and environmental setup might require adjustments to facilitate optimal participation and benefits.

Some of the goals of Adapted Physical Education include:

- 1) Promote the development of skills needed for the use of school and community playgrounds, e.g., balancing, swinging, climbing, hanging, hopping, and basketball.
- 2) Deliver physical fitness and activities that will increase/maintain endurance, flexibility, and strength, e.g., power walking, weight training, aerobic exercises, etc.
- 3) Promote the acquisition of the social skills necessary for following directions, fair play, sportsmanship, and respecting the rights of others.
- 4) Promote the development of physical and social skills needed to participate in after-school and/or community programs such as Special Olympics, Paralympics, or Deaflympics.
- 5) Promote the transfer of the physical and social skills needed for leisure/recreational activities for use at school and in the community.

Many researches have shown that physical education programs can do a great deal to improve the lifestyle of children with disabilities including individuals with hearing impairment; Physical Education can increase competency in gross motor skills, help to control obesity, improve self-esteem and social skills, encourage an active lifestyle and maintain motivation in various areas (Philip, 2007). APE can be utilized for many disability categories. Among them are individuals with hearing impairment, physical disabilities, visual impairment, intellectual disabilities, autism, and behavioral and emotional disturbance are some of them. From the above disabilities' categories, this research mainly revolves around the issue of individuals with hearing impairment.

2.1.2. *Hearing Impairment*

According to Kirk et al., (2009) hearing loss is defined by the degree of loss, the type of loss, and the age at which the loss occurred. Deafness is defined as a hearing impairment that is severe enough that the child cannot process linguistic information through hearing, even when using amplification or hearing aids this hearing loss adversely affects a child's educational performance. Being hard of hearing is defined as an impairment in hearing that may be permanent or fluctuating and that adversely affects a child's educational performance but that is not included under the definition of deafness. According to Luo (2000) there are two types

of hearing loss, namely deaf and hard of hearing. Deaf means when hearing is insufficient for comprehension of auditory information, with or without the use of a hearing aid and hard of hearing refers to a hearing loss that makes understanding speech difficult but not impossible.

2.2. The Educational Practice of Physical Education for Students with Hearing Impairment

Gizachew (2012) stated that physical education in schools is one important setting for achieving the goals of a healthy lifestyle. To fulfill the objectives of physical education as well as other education, the curriculum should be designed based on students' needs. Persons with hearing impairment can receive the same benefits as their peers without disability if adapted sports and activities are included in the school sports program (Gizachew, 2012).

Additionally, to know the educational practices that are done regarding physical education to students with disabilities one must go through the following perspectives. These perspectives are identification mechanisms, teaching strategies, opportunities, and challenges related to the educational practice of physical education for students with hearing impairment.

2.2.1. Identification Mechanism of Students with Hearing Impairment

Although the need for early identification of disability is evident, the current state of routine screening practice needs intensive training of screeners before more rigorous techniques are implemented (Muga, 2003). The question of how the students are identified for assessment requires critical attention. Because there is a certain procedure that one practitioner must undergo. There are at least two ways in which a student may be identified for assessment. The first is that the school suspects the presence of a learning or behavior problem and asks the student's parents for permission to evaluate the student individually. The second is the student's parent may also call or write to the school or the director of special education and request that their child be evaluated (Muga, 2003). After carefully identifying the student with any kind of detected disability the next thing is assessment. Assessment is also known as evaluation, and it can be seen as a problem-solving process that involves many ways of collecting information about the students. The assessment or information gathering process involves the following processes: Observing the student's interactions with parents, teachers, and peers; Interviewing the student and significant others in his or her life; Examining school records and past evaluations results; Evaluating developmental and medical histories; Using information from checklists completed by parents, teachers, or by the student; Evaluating curriculum requirement

and options; and Evaluating the student's type and rate of learning during trial teaching periods (Salvia et. al, 2010).

2.2.2. Teaching Strategies of Physical Education for Students with Hearing Impairment

According to Torreno, (2019), since each student differs in degrees of impairment and ability, teaching strategies must be individualized according to need. Although PE is an area that is difficult to accommodate and modify for certain disabilities, many options make learning more accessible. As Vize (2019) suggested these options can be: establishing a 'stop and look' strategy which is based on a visual signal, teaching the class using a predictable pattern of activities, and establishing an emergency signal.

For creating a favorable condition in the participation of students with hearing impairment in physical education classes, strategies were necessary for different aspects of the same class. Successful strategies were actions that had a teaching purpose, reached the student's functionality, and respected the characteristics, needs, and potentialities of the student (Fiorini and Manzini, 2017).

Moreover, National and international studies contemplate strategies that PE teachers could use in regular classes and practical classes when there is SWHI in the class. The note deals with four types of strategies: to make adaptations; to instruct the activity; to communicate with the SWHI and to use peer tutors (Auxter et al., 2010). Concerning adapting, the Physical Education teacher may modify the rules of an activity and add some visual information to the auditory signals. Concerning strategies to instruct the activity, the following possibilities were suggested: to provide physical assistance, that is, to guide the student's movement; to observe the student's response, after the explanation; and to repeat the instruction in different ways (Fiorini and Manzini, 2017).

The strategies recommended to the Physical Education teachers to communicate with students with hearing impairment were: to speak face to face to the student to stimulate lip reading; to use facial expressions and gestures concomitantly; and to create signals that are easy to recognize and see to communicate at a distance. With the presence of a peer tutor, the conditions for giving attention to the students with hearing impairment and the time spent participating in an activity would be better (Auxter et al., 2010). Also, any disability should not exclude students from participating in any activities. Depending on a student's disability a separate, adaptive class or

modification within a typical class can offer access to physical education (torreno, 2019). Arranging the environment with easy access to supplies can prevent accidents and improve participation in activities. Also working with paraprofessionals and individual encouragement can promote learning and ease frustration over physical difficulties (Torreno, 2019).

Similarly, Vize (2019) explained that children with a hearing impairment have varying needs in physical education class depending upon their level of hearing loss and their preferred communication methods. Some children may have some hearing, which is supplemented by hearing aids, while others may have no functional hearing.

2.2.3. Opportunities to Teach Physical Education to Students with Hearing Impairment

Today, the idea of individuals with disabilities being able to participate in sports and physical activity is not so uncommon. In many countries, opportunities exist from the grassroots to the elite level for individuals with a disability to showcase their abilities in sports and physical activity (fekede, 2012). Students with hearing impairment are participating in the Deaf Olympics competition that is organized by the International Committee of Sports for the Deaf (ICSD) (Audicus, 2014).

Under the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), adapted physical education is required for those SWDs who require specially designed instruction to receive physical education (Fekede, 2012). Teachers can significantly improve the educational outcomes of SWDs by implementing specific strategies. For example: a teacher's creativity can open new opportunities to learn (Torreno, 2019). From the above statement, one can say that getting access to APE is an opportunity in itself. Adapted physical education can maximize the benefit that one individual with a disability can get from Physical Education. Even though many opportunities are open for individuals with disabilities, in our country it seems an intangible idea to fulfill those opportunities.

2.2.4. Challenges Related to Teaching Physical Education to Students with Hearing Impairment

In Ethiopia, according to Gizachew, (2012), some of the challenges that are faced by students with disabilities regarding APE can be illustrated as follows:

Financial considerations have had several impacts on APE. For example: failure to provide new facilities; shortage of equipment; reductions in the number of physical education lessons and

timetable allocation and also inadequate facilities and poor maintenance of teaching sites. The other issue is the insufficiency and inadequacy of appropriately qualified PE teacher is widely evident. And also class size, Scheduling, and Training for physical education teachers can be considered as challenging issues. Additionally, there are some examples of how successful teaching practices should be implemented. These examples are key factors that are interdependent and essential for securing effective teaching practice, with an emphasis placed on their implementation in physical education. These key factors are Teachers' Attitudes, Supportive policy, Flexible curriculum, Community involvement, Supportive policy, Physical environment.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

3. Research Methods and Materials

3.1. Research Design

The approach that the researcher has used to accomplish this study is mixed. From the mixed approach, the researcher has selected an embedded design. Because embedded design enables the researcher to collect quantitative and qualitative data concurrently. Also, the researcher has questions that require different data-gathering methods, so embedded design is appropriate when a researcher has different questions that require different types of data (Creswell, 2012).

3.2. Populations of the Study

The population of the study includes the school principal, physical education teacher, and students with hearing impairment. The number of participants and grade level of students with hearing impairment are illustrated in table 1.

Table 1. The number of participants and Grade level of students with hearing impairment

Participants	Male	Female	Total
Physical education teacher	1	-	1
Students with hearing impairment	36	22	58
Principal	2	-	2
Total	39	22	61

Grade level of students with hearing impairment			
1 st	8	11	19
2 nd	7	8	15
3 rd	7	6	14
4 th	4	7	10
Total	26	32	58

As to describe table 1, There is only 1 male physical education teacher, and no female teacher is present. The total number of students with hearing impairment is 58, consisting of 36 male and 22 female students. This suggests a higher proportion of male students with hearing impairment in this particular setting. There are 2 male principals, and no female principals are involved. Overall, the total number of participants in the data is 61 (39 males and 22 females).

On Grade Distribution: The students with hearing impairment are spread across four grade levels. The number of students per grade varies: 1st Grade has the highest number of students (19 total: 8 males, 11 females). 2nd Grade follows closely with 15 total students (7 males, 8 females). 3rd Grade has 14 students (7 males, 6 females). 4th Grade has the least number of students (10 total: 4 males, 7 females). For most grades, there are more female students than male students, except for 1st and 3rd grades, where the male students outnumber the female students. Overall, there are more male participants (39) than female participants (22). This is

especially evident in the group of students with hearing impairment, where there are significantly more males (36) compared to females (22).

3.3. Sampling Technique

The participants were selected from the school by non-probability sampling. From non-probability sampling, a researcher has used purposive and comprehensive sampling. And researcher takes comprehensive sampling because some of the participants are small, so comprehensive sampling is best when the number of the population is small (Creswell, 2012).

The researcher has taken samples from the populations namely: the school principal, physical education teacher, and students with hearing impairment. By comprehensive sampling researchers have taken all of the students with hearing impairment, physical education teachers and the school principal.

3.4. Sample of the Study

The sample of participants that have been included in the study is illustrated in table 2.

Table 2. Sample of participants

Participants	Male	Female	Total
Principal	1	-	1
Physical Education Teacher	1	-	1
Students with Hearing Impairment	11	13	24
Total	13	13	26

3.5. Instruments

The tools or instruments that the researchers have used to conduct this research are questionnaires, structured interviews, and observation checklists. As these tools indicate the researcher's source of information mainly relies on primary sources rather than secondary sources.

4. Results and Discussion

This section tries to present, analyze, and interpret the collected data. The results of the study have been illustrated without losing their meanings and then a discussion was made by

comparing the results with literature. The researcher has narrated the data by forming five thematic issues and these issues are analyzed and discussed below.

4.1. Characteristics of Respondents

In this section, the researcher determines the characteristics of the respondents which included gender, and their academic positions.

In Table 3 revealed that there is 1 male school principal, 1 male physical education teacher, 11(45.83%) male students with hearing impairment, and 13(54.17%) female students with hearing impairment.

Table 3. Characteristics of the respondents

No	Participants	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Principal	1	100%	-	0	1	100%
2	Physical Education Teacher	1	100%	-	0	1	100%
3	Students with hearing impairment	11	45.83%	13	54.17%	24	100%

4.2. Identification of Students with Hearing Impairment in the School

The researcher has asked about the identification mechanism of the school in structured interview for the school principal. As the data from the structured interview depicted: Before Students with Hearing Impairment come to the school, the school’s principal in collaboration with other government bodies identifies students with hearing impairment. The way of identifying students with hearing impairment was by communicating with the education office, and social affairs and by traveling to country sides to raise awareness. After doing the above things, the school has managed to identify and gather students with hearing impairment under one roof. After the school enters the students, the school has thought about an in-depth identification of students with hearing impairment. i.e., the magnitude of hearing of students with hearing impairment. However, the school was unable to manage the identification of Students with Hearing Impairment’s hearing because of the inaccessibility of audiologists.

Identification of students with hearing impairment minimally requires: Observing students’ interactions with parents, teachers, and peers; Interviewing the student and significant others in his or her life; Examining school records and past evaluation results; Evaluating developmental and medical histories; Using information from checklists completed by parents, teachers, or by

the student; Evaluating curriculum requirement and options; and Evaluating the student's type and rate of learning during trial teaching periods (Salvia, 2010). Conversely, the principal's reply about the identification of Students with Hearing Impairment is in disagreement with the procedures that have to be taken.

4.3. Teaching Strategies Employed to Teach Students with Hearing Impairment in the School

Except for the questions in the structured interview for the school principal, all of the instruments have questioned the teaching strategies of the school. The results that are obtained from Questionnaires for students with hearing impairment have been analyzed as in Table 4.

As shown in Table 4, regarding participation in physical education practical classes about 20 (100%) of the student have witnessed that their physical education teacher motivates them in the teaching process of physical education. Regards teacher supports in areas where face some difficulties about 16 (80%) of students with hearing impairment have agreed on the support that their physical education teacher gives them in their difficulty areas and around 4 (20%) students with hearing impairment have not decided whether there is a support or not. Regards physical education teacher considers individual differences around 17 (85%) of students with hearing impairment have acknowledged that their physical education teacher considers individual differences, and about 2 (10%) of students with hearing impairment did not decide whether their teacher considers their difference or not and 1 (5%) students with hearing impairment didn't agree on the question.

In regards teacher shows the desired activities in a practical class by using sign language revealed that the school is successfully teaching physical education by using sign language because all 20 (100%) of the students with hearing impairment agreed on that specific question.

teacher utilizes different teaching methods that are appropriate to my ability like demonstration and lecturing methods showed that 15 (75%) of students with hearing impairment agreed that their teacher that he/she utilized different teaching methods for teaching them physical education, and 3 (15%) of students with hearing impairment have not yet decided on the issue of utilizing different teaching methods and 2 (10%) of students with hearing impairment have shown that their teacher didn't utilize any kind of teaching method to teach them physical education. Except for question number 2 of the questionnaire that is prepared for physical

education teachers, all 4 questions are targeted toward knowing the teaching strategies of the school.

Table 4. Teaching strategies of physical education for students with hearing impairment by percentage

No	Conditions of the school	Frequency	Percentage
1	My teacher motivates me to participate in physical education practical classes.	Agree – 20	100%
		Undecided – 0	0%
		Disagree – 0	0%
		Total – 20	
2	When I learn in the field the teacher supports me in areas where I face some difficulties.	Agree – 16	80%
		Undecided – 4	20%
		Disagree – 0	0%
		Total – 20	
3	My physical education teacher considers individual differences.	Agree 17	85%
		Undecided 2	10%
		Disagree 1	5%
		Total – 20	
4	My teacher shows the desired activities in a practical class by using sign language.	Agree – 20	100%
		Undecided - 0	0%
		Disagree – 0	0%
		Total – 20	
5	My teacher utilizes different teaching methods that are appropriate to my ability like demonstration and lecturing methods.	Agree – 15	75%
		Undecided – 3	15%
		Disagree – 2	10%

The first question is about the preparation of the lesson plan, and the teacher has answered “yes” to this question. In regards considers individual differences researcher found that the teacher didn’t allow students in activities other than the prescribed activities. The rest of the two questions are open-ended questions that ask about teaching strategies and the modification mechanism of the teacher. For the question regarding teaching strategy researcher has gained

the following answer: the teacher uses a teaching strategy that is mainly used by other regular physical education teachers teaching strategy like teacher centered method, demonstration, and lecturing method.

Similarly, the answer that the researcher obtained from the last question i.e., modification mechanism is that the teacher uses only sign language to modify the teaching process of physical education to students with hearing impairment. Finally, all the questions that have been listed in the observation checklist have also aimed to know the teaching strategy of the teacher towards teaching physical education to students with hearing impairment. As the researcher observed in the practical class, the teacher's ability to motivate and allow the students with hearing impairment to practice seems good. And also, the teacher has a good manner of conduct and willingness to listen to student's problems. Then the issue of identifying and considering individual differences of students with hearing impairment in the practical session of the lesson also seems good.

Moreover, the researcher has witnessed the teacher's use of teaching aids as there were ropes, balls, and pads. The teacher's ability to modify instructions for students with hearing impairment seems to focus on giving the preferred activities by using only sign language as a modification basis. And finally, the teacher also seems to pay attention to safety rules. Most of the above results about teaching strategies are inconsistent with many kinds of literature. As vise (2019), stated teachers can modify the classroom by establishing a 'stop and look' strategy which is based on a visual signal, teaching the class using a predictable pattern of activities, and establishing an emergency signal, using key signs for the activities that will be done in each term. As suggested by Torreno (2019), Arranging the environment with easy access to supplies can prevent accidents and improve participation in activities. Working with paraprofessionals and individual encouragement can promote the teaching practice of physical education and ease frustration over physical difficulties. Moreover, teachers can significantly improve the educational outcomes of students with disabilities by implementing specific strategies. For example: a teacher's creativity can open new opportunities to learn (Torreno, 2019).

4.4. Opportunities to Teach Physical Education for Students with Hearing Impairment in the School

To find reliable data about the opportunity of the school to teach physical education to students with hearing impairment the researcher has asked many kinds of questions by using different

kinds of data-gathering instruments like questionnaires and structured interviews. Now the researchers discussed it as follows:

Questions number 6-10 of the questionnaire for Students with Hearing Impairment have targeted to dig out about the opportunities of the school (Table 5).

Table 5. The opportunities of the school in percentage

No	Conditions of the school	Frequency	Percentage
6	My school administrators help me to participate in sports activities.	Agree – 10	50%
		Undecided – 10	50%
		Disagree – 0	0%
		Total – 20	
7	My school has enough teaching material that help me learn physical education	Agree – 13	65%
		Undecided – 7	35%
		Disagree – 0	0%
		Total – 20	
8	My school’s Physical structure is suitable for the teaching and learning process of physical education.	Agree – 20	100%
		Undecided – 0	0%
		Disagree – 0	0%
		Total – 20	
9	My family supports me with the necessary materials I need to participate?	Agree – 2	10%
		Undecided – 1	5%
		Disagree – 17	85%
		Total – 20	
10	My family encouraged me to participate in physical education classes.	Agree – 8	40%
		Undecided – 3	15%
		Disagree – 9	45%
		Total – 20	

As to describe Table 5, regarding participation in sports activities has yielded the answer that 10 (50%) of Students with Hearing Impairment have agreed upon the idea that there is a

commitment on the side of the school administrator to help them participate in sports activities and the rest of 10 (50%) of Students with Hearing Impairment have said vice versa. Enough teaching materials that help me learn physical education 13 (65%) of students with hearing impairment have agreed on the material provision that their school offers regarding physical education, and 7 (35%) Students with Hearing Impairment did not agree on that provision. Regards physical structure is suitable for the teaching and learning process of physical education 20 (100%) of students with hearing impairment have agreed that the physical structure of their school is suitable for them to do exercises. We have asked this question because of the predictability of having multiple disabilities like hearing impairment with physical disability. When we come to the necessary materials which need to participate about family support, around 2 (10%) of students with hearing impairment have agreed that their parents give them the necessary support they need to participate in the physical education class and 1 (5%) of students with hearing impairment have not decided on the support and the rest 17 (85%) Students with Hearing Impairment has disagreed on the question. This means most of the families of Students with Hearing Impairment did not acknowledge the benefits of physical education for their children.

Finally, regarding participation in physical education classes has also revealed that there is a low rate of family encouragement for students with hearing impairment regarding physical education practices because around 10 (50%) Students with Hearing Impairment disagreed with this specific question, and 7 (35%) of Students with Hearing Impairment has agreed and the rest of 3 (15%) students with hearing impairment have not decided yet.

From the questionnaire that the researcher has given to physical education teachers there was one question that tries to find out about the time allotment for the period of physical education and the answer to this specific question was a negative answer, which means that the time allotment for the physical education period is not enough as expected. As well from the structured interview that has been conducted, there are around 4 questions that try to find out about opportunities of the school towards teaching physical education for students with hearing impairment. The numbers of those questions are 1, 2, 5, and 6. In question number 1, the researcher has managed to find the answer that says *“the parents of students with hearing impairment come to the school once a month and at that time the school and parents negotiate about the overall welfare of students with hearing impairment including physical education.”* And the second question is about the collaboration of the school with other organizations:

Regarding the issue of physical education “*the school didn't have any kind of contact with other organizations.*”

The 5th question was direct because it asked the principal what opportunity the school possessed in the area of physical education. The reported was that “*we have acquired some sports materials like shoes, balls, and clothes from a foreign country called Ireland and also this country has made a promise to support the school in any kind of issue it faces.*”

The last question is about what the school did to maximize the participation of Students with Hearing Impairment in physical education. In this question researcher has concluded that the school has planned to extend the time allotment of physical education periods from only Tuesday and Friday to all the five working days of the week. The school has hired one individual with hearing impairment who is active in sports activities to train Students with Hearing Impairment in the afternoon sessions. The school has been notified to get support from the city administrator about the issue of physical education.

According to many kinds of literature (Torreno, 2019) it was stated that “to make the practice of teaching physical education for students with hearing impairment work, general classroom teachers, specialists, parents and students themselves must work together to create the best educational environment”. This means that many stakeholders including family must involve in the creation process of the best educational environment. Again as (Gizachew, 2012) stated “Scheduling” or time allotment is regarded as a challenging issue that controversies with the results that the researchers gained through the questionnaire for physical education teachers. So, the issue of time must be given due attention as well as other aspects. Furthermore, according to many literatures the notion of “familial involvement” is a mandatory thing to cultivate the practice of physical education for Students with Hearing Impairment to its peak level.

4.5. Challenges Related to Teaching Physical Education to Students with Hearing Impairment in the School

The researcher managed to ask about the challenges only the principal of the school via structured interview and it was also a direct statement that asked about what challenges the school faces in teaching physical education to students with hearing impairment. The district governor has less focus on the issue of physical education for Students with Hearing Impairment. There is limited knowledge about how students with hearing impairment can be

successful individuals in areas of physical education and the families of students with hearing impairment didn't collaborate with the school in maximizing the participation of their children in physical education sessions. As stated in much literature many other challenges can hinder the development of the practice of teaching physical education like Finance, shortage of equipment; Facilities, Qualified teaching personnel, Class size, Scheduling, and Training for physical education teachers (Gizachew, 2012).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

From the above-reviewed literature, one can conclude that physical education is an integral part of the total educational activities which is beneficial for mental, physical, social, and psychological aspects of an individual's life through planned and selected physical activities. Hence, based on the findings of the study researcher can conclude as follows:

- ✓ The school's practice of identifying students with hearing impairment seems to be less than expected and there is a shortage of audiologists.
- ✓ The teaching practice of physical education in the school has some hindrances to the rigidity of the teaching method. However, there is also some commitment in the school like teaching the students with hearing impairment in sign language.
- ✓ There is a low rate of family encouragement for students with hearing impairment regarding physical education practices.
- ✓ Even though there are some opportunities like commitment among the school in reforming the schedule regarding teaching physical education, there are still many opportunities that the school, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders can offer.
- ✓ The school district governor has less focus on the issue of physical education for students with hearing impairment, limited knowledge about how to accommodate the practice of teaching physical education for students with hearing impairment, and collaboration of parents with the school in maximizing the participation of their children in physical education sessions is all regarded as a challenge in Ambo Lazarist Catholic School for the Deaf.

Disclosure Statement

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